

UDC: 351.851(477)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3496881

Vavrenyuk Sergey Anatolievich

PhD in Public Administration, Doctoral student of Educational, Scientific and Production Center of the National University of Civil Protection of Ukraine, Kharkiv
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6396-9906

QUALITY OF EDUCATION AS ONE OF THE STATE SAFETY FACTORS

This article focuses on defining the role of education as one of the main security factors of the entire state. The author points out that education is aimed at ensuring security at all levels: individuals, society, and the state.

The article analyzes the tasks assigned to education for the security of the state as a whole. As a result, the author emphasizes the role and importance of education.

Much attention is paid to education as an object of security, which ensures the educational process and the education system functions as a social institution.

The author concludes that education acts simultaneously as an object, resource and means of state security and creates, strengthens the foundation for the future well-being of the nation

In conclusion, the author says that education can ensure the safe development of the younger generation.

Keywords: *quality of education, state security, national security, education system, role and importance of education.*

Problem statement. The current state of national security research is limited to either military-strategic or economic aspects, or narrowly applied sociological and psychological developments. If education was considered in the context of national

security, then, as a rule, problems were covered exclusively in the field of military education. In modern domestic science, systematic fundamental studies related to the socio-cultural component of national security are virtually absent.

Today, however, social and cultural foundations of ensuring its security in general and the problem of educational security, in particular, are extremely important for the state. It is necessary to determine with an understanding of the place of educational security in the general system of socio-cultural bases of ensuring national security of Ukraine.

Analysis of recent publications on research issues. National security issues were addressed by the following scientists: Nizhnik, A. Buteyko, A. Gutsal, O.M. Kostenko, however, did not thoroughly examine the impact of education on state security as a factor in national security.

Many scholars have considered the impact of military education on the national security of the state, determined the place and role of education in understanding the security and defense policy of the state.

Purpose of the article. The purpose of this article is to highlight topical issues of national security through the development of educational space in the country.

Presenting the main material of research. The system of modern society includes the basic subsystems, one of which is education. Reflection on any socio-cultural process leads to a rethinking of the role and place of education in public life. This is due to the growing influence of education systems on other spheres of public life, starting with the socialization of the individual, the processes of progress that determine the history of the nation and the state, and ending with the security of society, including the national.

In the scientific literature, the term "education" is ambiguous. Each researcher considers it in the framework of their scientific problem, focusing on one or the other side of this concept:

- as a social phenomenon, a constant companion of mankind along the way of its historical development;
- as significant value (social and individual);
- as a function of society and the state in relation to its citizens and at the same time a function of citizens in relation to its own development;
- as a complex hierarchical system that includes different levels of education;
- as an area of life of a society that contains not only the sphere of education but also other close areas - culture, leisure and activities;
- as an activity based on the interaction of the teacher and the subject of educational influence;
- as a process of learning and the result of educational activities.

Also, education is understood to mean “purposeful activity that involves some form of communication aimed at learning”, the content of which is:

- communication: the interaction of two or more persons or a non-living mediator and people involved in the process of information transfer (messages, ideas, knowledge, principles). Communication can be produced, non-verbal, direct, mediated and can be achieved through the involvement of various means and channels of communication;
- training: individual acquisition of knowledge or modification of information, knowledge, understanding, worldview, value attitudes, skills, competences or behavior based on experience, practice, training or teaching;
- organized activity: structurally or in a certain sequence planned to achieve explicit or implicit goals. Provision is made for a provider institution that creates the conditions for learning and the application of teaching methods within which communication is carried out;
- purposeful: the educational process is characterized by duration and continuity.

The education system must ensure the current and future human resources of the state, guaranteeing its intellectual independence in all spheres of social production and

social life. In particular, according to the well-known sociologist G.F. Shafranova-Kutsev, the scale of higher education in Ukraine does not meet the determined rates of socio-economic development of the state until 2020. World experience shows that in order for the innovative economy to function properly, at least half of the country's employed population must have a college degree. Currently, only 30 percent of the Ukrainian population has such education with an annual increase of no more than 0.3 percent. Moreover, the main increase is largely due to the correspondence form of training, second higher education, and distance education. Therefore, proposals to reduce the number of students in domestic higher education institutions are simply unsuccessful, as they will not ensure the implementation of a long-term program of socio-economic development of Ukraine for the period until 2020.

Promulgated in the law "On education" the priority of the education sector, education as a purposeful process of education and training in the interests of the individual, society, state, the right to education as one of the fundamental and inalienable constitutional rights of the citizens of Ukraine can be real, meaningful, effective only in security conditions. Violation of security due to natural disasters, economic stagnation, social shocks or external pressure complicates, in the extreme case - makes it impossible to implement.

Of course, the education system exists and continues to function in a critical situation. However, under the pressure of circumstances, she faces many problems that have a destructive effect on her. Yes, demand for people with diplomas is falling today. According to forecasts, up to 50% of graduates of higher education institutions in 2020 will not find use in the labor market.

The feedback between education and national security is due to the fact that the security of Ukraine is provided by the people. It is crucially determined by the human factor. However, it is the high school that serves as a medium for the formation of the individual, his or her outlook and, therefore, shapes the intellectual, moral, labor potential of society, its ability to ensure its own development and safety. It is worth

agreeing with S.V. Kamyshev, who states that the state's security is strategically determined by the state of the education system. The education system is the environment and sphere, the most important mechanism of comprehensive development, mobilization and actualization of intellectual potential, as well as innovative development. In industrialized countries, up to 40% of the gross national product increase is received at its expense. And Ukraine's national security depends directly on the educational background of the youth of the 21st century, their moral and political ideals, social values, level of general culture and training.

Education is aimed at ensuring security at all levels: the individual, society, the state. It plays an essential role in strengthening its entire species. Thus, without qualified personnel, economic and military security of the state is impossible; technological security is unthinkable without scientific development. In today's conditions, the only way to increase Ukraine's power is to preserve, develop and mobilize the intellectual potential of the state. Its future has to do with the transition to an innovative path of development that makes it difficult to overestimate the role of education.

The security education system solves three task vectors. First, it equips each person with the knowledge, skills, and skills needed to ensure personal safety, and forms a culture of security. As an example, the discipline "Safety of Life" in higher education. It is equally important that in the learning process, a person learns and becomes accustomed to performing his or her functional duties to act responsibly and competently, taking into account public safety interests. This is achieved through legal, environmental, political education and upbringing.

Secondly, the education system trains professionals professionally engaged in providing specific types and areas of security. It is clear that identifying and tracking certain types of hazards, developing and implementing measures to prevent them, neutralize them, eliminate them requires different tools and tools, different knowledge and experience, different structures and individuals. For example, the same people, the

same structure cannot assess, and influence the seismic, sanitary-epidemiological, military-political, criminogenic situation. Employees of law enforcement, environmental, military, rescue services are trained by completely different programs, methods, algorithms. That is why the education system in Ukraine includes departmental institutions of higher education and organization, or to the contrary: different departments have their own educational institutions, which train staff for themselves and other structures that need specialists of the relevant profile. The network of such institutions plays an important role in the need for adult retraining and retraining.

Third, training and retraining of personnel in the field of security system organization is extremely important. These are professionals, officials whose task is to organize and ensure the safe functioning of a particular security object - be it an enterprise (institution), group (community), territory or state as a whole. These may include, for example, the Deputy Director of Security, the Chief of Security, a member of a state or public committee, a department, a commission, and others. Today, the country has a fairly extensive network of training centers, which are trained, so-called "security managers" and is complex, fundamental and applied.

The status of education as a resource of human and social capital, having a society and personality at its disposal, gaining new opportunities for development, meeting interests and needs, anticipates the growing demands for the development of the education system. The modern state needs educated, creative people, enterprising, sociable, competitive, and able to navigate constantly changing conditions of life.

The content of education is determined by social needs, so in modern conditions, the content of knowledge is rapidly changing, its volume is increasing, and the need for a particular type of knowledge is changing. The development of education is greatly influenced by the processes of globalization and informatization. There is an evolution of education into the main source of income in the information society, as economic development is determined by modern technologies and innovations. In the post-

industrial economy, the most in-demand specialists are not just possessing modern knowledge, skills and skills, but strive to constantly improve their skills, to undergo retraining, to introduce innovative technologies.

The development of the state is accompanied by a process of reforming the education system, which is interested in making quality education accessible to all social groups. In most modern democratic countries, education is compulsory and free. The state is interested in the students in the process of education to learn the system of values that is characteristic of this society.

The main purpose of education is the process of socialization of the individual. Socialization involves the assimilation of a wide range of cultural values, on the basis of which people's daily lives and development are ensured. Education can be defined as a formal process of transferring values, knowledge, skills and skills to the young generation. Raising children in the spirit of recognition of cultural values and ideals that have developed in society helps to support the existing social order.

Through education, cultural values are preserved and passed on from generation to generation. Yes, the modern school is actually a "genetic matrix of culture", through which generations of people are educated and educated. In this case, the transition to a new type of culture, as is the case in modern society, involves a fundamental restructuring, reforming the education system. Institutions of higher education, not only through the socialization of the individual, offer the assimilation of cultural values, but also introduce into the minds of the younger generation a system of social norms, rules of conduct, communication skills.

Consideration of education as a resource of social capital is that modern education contributes to the development of democracy. It is focused on overcoming national, racial, religious, social issues. The current education system aims to involve the younger generation of citizens in the values of democracy, teach them to be tolerant, to be able to make and take decisions for themselves, to live in the conditions of choice, not to be influenced by demagogues and populists.

Of great importance for a democratic state is the fulfillment of the educational function of a "social elevator", on the basis of which vertical social mobility in society is possible. Access to education allows representatives of lower social strata to improve their social status through higher education, promotion, and holding elected positions. In this case, education is both practical and symbolic.

People use the knowledge, skills and competences acquired in the course of education to achieve practical goals, while simultaneously possessing certificates, diplomas, certificates of education and training are indicators of prestige, a symbol of higher social status.

But in one way or another, in today's context, education is the most dynamic factor influencing economic and social processes: people's lifestyles, quality of life, cultural exchange, social and political interaction, sustainable economic development. It is in this sphere that the foundations of strategic development of the state, society and personality are laid.

The role and importance of education in the national security system is also determined by the environment and the mechanism of preserving, reproducing the national (civic and ethnic) identity of a society consisting of its individuals and groups. The Concept of National Security states that Ukraine's national interests in the spiritual sphere are to preserve and strengthen the moral values of society, the traditions of humanism and patriotism. Threats to society in this area are the devaluation of spiritual values and the decline of the spiritual and moral potential of society. The Information Security Doctrine also referred to the threats as "disorganization and destruction of the system of accumulation and preservation of cultural values".

The education and training system plays a strategically important role in preserving and restoring the culture of our country. It not only conveys to young people a certain amount of value-neutral information, sustained in the spirit of scientific and technological determinism, but it generates respect for their state, for its past, for the older generations. This task is all the more important because in the conditions of

globalization, geopolitical rivalry is aggravated and forms of rigid information and psychological confrontation in which massive attacks on our history, culture and way of life are made. The education system, through its positive work on forming a socially active and responsible person, in which a highly developed sense of dignity is realized in patriotic service to the Motherland, acts as a powerful mechanism for neutralizing these threats and strengthening the national security of Ukraine.

Another direction of the interconnectedness of these phenomena is determined by the fact that the education system itself is an object of security. Considering this provision, we distinguish three positions:

- the first captures attention to the physical safety of the educational institution and the persons involved in it. The safety of an educational institution is defined as “the condition of preserving the life and health of students, pupils and employees, as well as the material values of the educational institution from possible accidents, fires, accidents and other emergencies;

- the second relates to the process and mode of learning, above all, the accessibility and simplicity of teaching material for all students. However, it has to be stated that the learning process has a negative impact on the health of students, since the learning load they are experiencing is often incomparable to their age and functionality. In recent years, education has been undergoing a process of changing the educational paradigm. The new paradigm emphasizes the importance and relevance of protecting and promoting the health of students, which is seen as one of the basic principles of education. In order to implement such installations, various ways and means of optimizing the educational process are offered;

- the third position concerns the organization and functioning of the education system as a social institution. Threats to it have different nature, sources, and forms. Let's just say about them by a simple list. Crisis in the field of spirituality; decline in the authority of education, above all fundamental; Attempts to radically break the old system of education and recycle it in the model of developed countries of the West;

insufficient funding; commercialization of education. All this explains the need for a deep reform of the entire education system. We need a new educational strategy, the formation of state policy in the field of spiritual and moral education of the population.

Thus, education plays an enormous and growing role in the national security system. It acts simultaneously as its object, resource and means and creates, strengthens the foundation for the future prosperity of the nation as well as the security of the state. That is why the development of the education sector should be one of the important priorities of national security policy.

Conclusions and prospects for further research. The system of modern society includes the basic subsystems, one of which is education. Reflection on any socio-cultural process leads to a rethinking of the role and place of education in public life. This is due to the growing influence of education systems on other spheres of public life, starting with the socialization of the individual, the processes of progress that determine the history of the nation and the state, and ending with the security of society, including the national.

Speaking about modern Ukraine, it can be noted that it is a society of social polarization, which causes different opportunities for young people to reach a certain level of education, which in turn affects its level and quality of life. Education has always been, and remains, a major factor in social mobility, so that the educational status of young people is not only a significant criterion for their social development, but also one of the ways of confronting the dangers and risks of society, and therefore education can ensure the safe development of the young generation.

REFERENCES:

1. Vlasjuk O.S. "National Security of Ukraine: The Evolution of Domestic Policy Issues [Nacionalna bezpeka Ukrayini: evolyuciya problem vnutrishnoyi politiki]." *Selected. Sciences. Proceedings*. Kiev: NISD, 2016. Print

2. Sitnik G.P. "Public administration in the field of national security [Derzhavne upravlinnya u sferi nacionalnoyi bezpeki]." Kiev: The Russian Word, 2012. Print
3. Martinova L.B. "Problems of ensuring the competitiveness of human capital in Ukraine [Problemi zabezpechennya konkurentospromozhnosti lyudskogo kapitalu v Ukrayini]." *ZhSTU Bulletin*. 1 (79) (2017): 157-160. Print
4. Musienko I.I. "Education and security: to the problems of realization of national interests in the sphere of education]." *Bulletin of the Kharkov National Pedagogical University named after GS Skovoroda. Philosophy*. 39 (2012): 129-140.
5. Klein J. I. U.S. Education Reform and National Security (Independent Task Force Report No. 68). *New York: Council on Foreign Relations Press*, March (2012): 120.